

Supplementary materials 1: Invitation letter to participants

Participant Invitation to a Delphi study

Oslo, 18.09.2023

Dear X,

We are writing to invite you to take part in a Delphi study, which is the second of three studies that will be performed to create a tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies.

Before you decide whether or not you would like to take part, it is important for you to consider why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of the project?

In vitro studies are becoming an increasingly important source of data in risk assessment of chemicals, in the process to reduce the use of animals in toxicity testing. As part of the gradual incorporation and transition toward the use of new approach methodologies (NAMs), a framework for evidence-based use of NAMs in toxicological research and chemical risk assessment is required. With our project, we aim to contribute to the development of such a framework for evidence-based use of NAMs in human health hazard identification and characterisation. The first step is the development of a tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies. Internal validity is the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have prevented bias. Bias are systematic errors resulting in deviations from the truth in results or inference, and for *in vitro* studies such errors may be introduced in the study design, conduction, and/or analysis, and cause the result to be an overestimate or underestimate.

The tool will be useful for inclusion of NAMs in systematic literature reviews and risk assessments.

What is the purpose of the Delphi study?

The objective of the Delphi study is to have expert interpretation of the importance of different characteristics of study design, conduct, and analysis for introduction of bias into the results or inference of *in vitro* studies.

How are the Delphi study organised?

A two-round digital Delphi survey will be conducted (~4 hours per round), followed by an online workshop for guided discussions (~1 hours). In both Delphi rounds, expert panellists will complete an online survey, and we will use the data to identify expert agreement on characteristics important for introduction of bias into the results or inference of *in vitro* studies. Characteristics for which agreement were not reached during the two Delphi rounds will be discussed in the workshop. In addition, the participants will be asked to give input on the wording of the questions in each Delphi round and during the guided discussion. A project group member will lead the guided discussion in the workshop.

The participants will have some experience with systematic literature review principles and be working with a variety of *in vitro* models to cover a wide range of experimental systems. We also aim to include participants affiliated in the academia, governmental, and private research institutions, that are from a range of countries, and to have a gender balance.

Why have you been invited to take part?

We are looking to recruit 20-30 participants. To be eligible to participate all invited participants must confirm that they fulfil the following criteria:

- Some experience with systematic literature review principles.
- Active in the field of *in vitro* research in academia, governmental institution (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes), private research institution, self-employed.
- PhD degree completed.
- Fluent English speaker.

As an established expert who fulfils the above criteria, we are keen to gain your views about the importance of different characteristics of study design, conduct, and analysis for introduction of bias into the results or findings of *in vitro* studies.

What will you be asked to do if you take part?

The Delphi study will be performed in the period October 2023 to January 2024 (see Table for tentative timepoints for the Delphi rounds and the workshop).

Date	Oct 23-nov 5	Nov 6-Nov 24	Nov 27-Dec 10	Dec 11 – Jan 5	Jan 8-Jan 19
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What	Delphi round 1 (a reminder will be sent after one week)	Data analysis and feedback to participants	Delphi round 2 (a reminder will be sent after one week)	Data analysis and feedback to the participants	Workshop
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If you agree to be a participant in this Delphi study, you will need to tell us:

- That you fulfil the eligibility criteria.
- That you are available and willing to complete two questionnaires (Delphi round 1 and 2).
- If you believe your involvement in this project might present any potential conflicts of interest.

As an accepted participant in this Delphi study, you must not discuss your involvement, or any of the information shared with you during the project with anyone other than the research team.

Participants in the study are eligible to be co-authors of the Delphi study manuscript if they also read and comment on the final draft. No compensation or other incentives are offered for the participation.

Withdrawal procedure

Participants are free to request their withdrawal from the Delphi study at any point. Participants are asked to communicate their withdrawal request via email to Dr Gro Haarklou Mathisen. The request should state whether the withdrawal is because of:

- A personal issue
- A professional conflict with the study

No further information regarding reasons for the withdrawal will be requested.

Who is organizing and funding the research?

The project is led by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment, and the project lead is Dr Gro Haarklou Mathisen. The project is part of the work in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) project "Next Generation Risk Assessment in Practice".

The project receives funding from PARC HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-03, Grant [101057014].

Confidentiality

The Delphi study will not require personal information to be entered and therefore no personal information will be collected. All responses received will be strictly confidential, and only anonymised summary data will be shared.

Data protection

The Delphi rounds will be carried out as online surveys. The workshop will be carried out as online meeting and will be recorded. Transcripts of the workshop discussions will be machine-generated. Anonymised transcripts will be shared as raw data.

Data will be stored for the duration of the research project only and then deleted. Following completion of this study, only anonymised summary data will be kept and shared via an Open Science Framework platform on a journal website in accordance with the journals publication policy requirements.

Research ethics

The proposed Delphi study abides by the ethical requirements of the Norwegian Institute of Public Health, approved February 2023.

What do you do now?

Thank you for reading this information and for considering taking part in this research. Please let us know whether or not you would like to be a participant by replying to this email. If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Best Wishes,

Gro Haarklou Mathisen, on behalf of the research team